

A Networked Control System for Heterogeneous Robots

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Abstract—*To replace numerous platform-specific operator control units, this paper presents a design methodology and implementation for a low-cost, networked control system for heterogeneous robots that is chassis and operator control unit independent. By leveraging small embedded computers, we can control and connect various platforms through an existing wireless infrastructure and implement semi-autonomous capabilities for obstacle detection and avoidance. Our approach uses a standardized control system that connects to existing robots in a plug-and-play manner. Our programmable and adaptable controller can be applied to a wide variety of sectors such as military, law enforcement, and search and rescue. Regardless of the sector, an urgent need exists to meet the current challenges of unmanned system interoperability. We achieve a level of standardization between various platforms in order to incorporate greater levels of compatibility and autonomy.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Department of Defense continues to develop, procure and field robotic platforms, commonly referred to as UGVs (unmanned ground vehicles), for a myriad of missions to include force protection, reconnaissance, explosive detection, and disposal. Most current military robotic systems use directed control (teleoperation and waypoint-oriented control) requiring a full-time operator. The U.S. military currently uses these systems in Iraq and Afghanistan to perform jobs that are either too hazardous or are impossible for soldiers. All of these platforms require at least one operator constantly monitoring the progress of the robot through an operator control unit (OCU). Platforms include the iRobot® Packbot®, the Foster-Miller TALON™, the Allen-Vanguard™ Mk II and the Mesa Robotics Matilda™. None of these platforms have interchangeable parts and each has a specific OCU that is exclusive to the respective system. Each of these systems has its own communication frequencies, protocols, processors and interfaces for sensors. At present almost no two are alike or for that matter interoperable. The result is that soldiers must learn how to operate a different OCU with each platform and because of proprietary communication protocols the systems cannot operate without its own controller.

Many of these problems are due to the expediency when these systems were fielded. Military commanders on the ground in Iraq and Afghanistan needed solutions immediately rather than enduring the lengthy military acquisition process.

Future Combat Systems (FCS) will alleviate many of the problems with interoperability but that reality is still years away. FCS has set milestones for fielding unmanned, remotely controlled technology such that by 2015, one-third of the operational ground combat vehicles of the Armed Forces are unmanned [1]. With this initiative, there are many advantages to develop unmanned systems for both the civilian and military sectors. FCS will be able to network existing systems, those already under development, and systems yet to be developed. Networked UGVs will be an integral part of the future force.

We propose a means to enable different robotic platforms to operate on a common system. There are numerous advantages to networking UGVs and augmenting existing control systems and platforms. A generalized control system will allow a user to operate the UGV if the manufacturer's proprietary OCU becomes damaged or is missing. Additional sensors can be easily added using off-the-shelf microprocessors that have multiple I/O ports. With new sensors, different operating modes can be introduced to include autonomous navigation, object tracking, and obstacle detection and avoidance. This standardization would help "to achieve broad interoperability" and help to facilitate the advancement of unmanned systems [2]. We seek to achieve a level of standardization between the various platforms in order to incorporate autonomy. With our low-cost approach, we also hope to inspire others to do research with military and domestic UGVs as well.

We present our design and implementation of a generalized networked robotic controller for small, heterogeneous UGVs with an emphasis on military platforms. This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes related projects and work in controlling UGVs. Section 3 describes our methodology and evaluation of UGVs to determine what critical systems must be in our controller. Sections 4, 5, and 6, detail our system design in terms of hardware, network configuration, and software, respectively. Section 7 describes a number of heterogeneous system

implementations. Finally, Section 8 presents our conclusions and opportunities for future work.

2. RELATED WORK

Many research groups are working on a common controller for multiple, heterogeneous robotic platforms. Specifically, ARDEC (Armament Research, Development, and Engineering Center) in Picatinny, NJ has done extensive work on networking military robots with custom hardware and a targeting system control infrastructure. Space and Naval Warfare Systems Center, San Diego has developed an unmanned vehicle and sensor operator control interface capable of controlling and monitoring multiple sets of heterogeneous systems simultaneously [3]. They have also worked on numerous man-portable UGVs to enhance autonomy and communications in areas such as SLAM (simultaneous localization and mapping) and emplacing leave-behind sensors and communication links. At the University of Pennsylvania, the multiple autonomous robots (MARS) testbed features unmanned ground and aerial vehicles [4]. Similarly, the RoboFlag testbed at Cornell University incorporates multiple small robots to perform a cooperative task [5].

3. BACKGROUND

As part of our preliminary development stage, we identified, analyzed and evaluated existing military robotic platforms. The most common UGVs currently in use by the military are small, low-profile robots mounted on miniature tank treads. Every system we have evaluated involves an operator, a control unit and a chassis. Regarding the chassis itself, most of these platforms have very similar characteristics in the areas of transportability, ruggedness, speed, payload, mobility and power management. Therefore, we focused on comparing the communication protocols between the OCU and the chassis, the user input and feedback at the operator level and the sensor packages on each platform.

3.1. Existing Military UGVs

We focused on three robotic platforms that are currently being used or have been used in Iraq and Afghanistan: the Foster-Miller TALON™, iRobot® Packbot®, and the Mesa Robotics Matilda™.

All these systems are propelled by DC motors. Due to the amount of current required to drive these motors, a system of current directing circuits is required. Typical circuits used to drive these motors can be simple or complicated H-bridges or a system of relays. As for feedback and position sensing, the platforms vary; they all use some sort of feedback to assist in drive control, however, not all have position sensors. Regardless, each platform uses similar signals yet different protocols to control motor functions.

Nearly all of these small UGVs have dedicated, direct, line-of-sight, proprietary communication protocols. A typical configuration can include multiple channels for data and video using a wireless link directly from the OCU to the chassis. Line-of-sight distances can extend to 500 meters and tethered communications can range a few hundred meters [6]. However, since they are line-of-sight connections, the data and video connections are severely degraded or cutoff altogether in buildings or tunnels.

Figure 1 – Foster-Miller TALON™ with OCU

We also evaluated the sensor suites for each platform. Almost all of the platforms have multiple cameras. They also include a variety of sensors such as audio and video surveillance and chemical agent detection. Some platforms provide battery life levels, wheel/shaft encoders and compass accelerometers for tracking distance and direction [7]. Regardless of the sensor, the camera continues to be the primary feedback mechanism to the operator. These cameras are high resolution and high frame rate, requiring large amounts of bandwidth and therefore are transmitted on gigahertz frequencies.

3.2. Methodology

We used our knowledge of existing military UGVs to develop a network-based system which was simple for the user to implement and easy for the developer to maintain. We also sought a system that was relatively inexpensive and resource efficient which could meet operational mission requirements. As a prototype model, we utilized commercial off the shelf (COTS) technology as a proof of concept. In our analysis, we determined our controller must be IEEE 802.11b/g-capable in order to interface to our existing wireless infrastructure, use a web-based graphical user interface (GUI) launched from any PC or laptop on the network and have a USB camera for ease of integration and to keep costs at a minimum. We also determined that our embedded computer must have host USB capabilities and can implement the IEEE 802.11b/g protocol. We chose to leverage the IEEE 802.11 standard primarily due to its widespread use and the existing infrastructure at our organization. These baseline requirements can allow almost

any researcher to duplicate our control system at a very low monetary cost.

4. UGV CONTROL SYSTEM

Our system integrates a client-side front-end interface with a back-end server to provide operational control of the remote robotic platform. Specifically, a user connects to a relay server via a standard web interface, selects an available robot and utilizes a Java-based graphical user interface to teleoperate the remote system. A USB camera provides video feedback to the operator. The control hardware allows for a modular system that communicates over existing wireless and wired local area networks. The GUI, relay server and embedded computer all operate using IP and TCP/IP protocols. Communications within the robot chassis are via RS-232 connections.

Figure 2 – Hardware Block Diagram

4.1. Embedded Computer

We evaluated a number of processors to include the Gumstix embedded computer and other ARM and x86 architectures, however our final design uses the Qwerk embedded computer for the high-level functionality in our system – namely communications over our local network and video processing. The Qwerk was designed by the Robotics Institute at Carnegie Mellon University and Charmed Labs LLC. With host USB support, installed drivers, a hardened case, and an extensive open-source software repository, the Qwerk offered the best solution for our system. In order to make our design more modular, we did not use most of the low-level I/O capabilities of the

Qwerk. However, the Qwerk does have a wide range of I/Os to include 4 motor controllers, 16 servo controllers, 16 programmable digital general purpose I/Os, 8 12-bit analog inputs, one 10/100BT Ethernet port and audio support. We did utilize the 2 RS-232 ports and 2 USB 2.0 host ports for connecting standard USB peripherals. The Qwerk integrates a 200 MHz ARM9 RISC microprocessor, 32 Mbytes SDRAM for data storage and 8 Mbytes of flash memory for program storage. The ARM9 processor runs Linux 2.6 with wireless networking (802.11b/g) and webcam video support [8]. The I/O interface is handled by a Xilinx Spartan 3E FPGA.

4.2. Wireless Networking and Video

We leverage existing wireless and wired networks at our organization for all of our communications. With the preponderance of IEEE 802.11 interface cards and access points, this standard was the most efficient choice. Our embedded computer supports WEP (wired equivalent privacy) encryption with device drivers for numerous network interface cards for ad hoc networking. In a military or law-enforcement environment, more secure encryption methods would need to be used. We chose various USB wireless NICs (network interface card) based on their small size, existing driver support, and low cost. For video, we utilized the Logitech Communicate STX Camera. We chose this device for the same reasons – cost, size and driver support.

4.3. In-System Communications

All of the communications between our processor and microcontroller are handled through an RS-232 serial port. Command instructions and feedback information are passed bidirectionally using this single, direct link. Our serial port was configured to 8 bits, no parity, 1 stop bit and 38400 baud. The microcontroller requires a level shifter to step-up the I/O port signals to RS-232 voltages. We implemented a simple protocol that consisted of a start byte (0xF0), followed by a command or sensor number, and ending with a command or sensor value.

4.4. Embedded Controller

For our low-level control and sensor integration, we used the Robostix microcontroller board. With the Atmel ATmega128 microcontroller running at 16 MHz, the Robostix provides a large number of I/O pins that are easily accessible. Its small form-factor (80 x 36 mm), low power consumption (32 mA active supply current at 5V and a 16 MHz operating frequency) and low cost (\$49) make it ideal for embedded applications. Some of the relevant I/O ports are the 6 PWM channels, 2 UARTs, and 8 ADC channels. This single board package provides the necessary control and interfacing for the servos, 2 UARTs and analog sensors in our system. General purpose I/Os, interrupt-driver input capture pins and other headers can also be utilized if needed [9].

4.5. Sensors and Servos

Since most UGVs have integrated sensors tied to a particular platform in a proprietary manner, we developed our own suite of infrared and ultrasonic sensors to allow our controller to be platform-independent. We integrated 3 Sharp GP2D12 infrared sensors and one Parallax PING ultrasonic sensor for obstacle detection and avoidance. These sensors are used to assist in navigation and for crude localization. They connect to the 3-pin headers on the Robostix to provide a differential voltage or in the case of the ultrasonic sensor, a signal pin to initiate and measure the time of the ultrasonic pulse. Standard 180 degree servos are used for the pan-tilt mechanism for the camera and for the sweeping motion of the ultrasonic sensor. The Robostix processes the sensor data and then continuously transmits the data in simple packets back to the embedded computer. All of the sensors and servos are powered with a 5V regulator located on the Robostix.

Figure 3 – System Mounted on Matilda (minus camera)

As noted, the total cost for our control system is extremely low with parts totaling just over \$500. These costs do not include the cost of the chassis itself. This bill of materials demonstrates that almost anyone can acquire the needed hardware to interface to a small UGV.

Item	Cost
Qwerk embedded computer	\$349
Robostix microcontroller	\$49
Logitech webcam	\$45
Wireless NIC	\$19
Ultrasonic Ranging Module	\$36
IR Sensors (3)	\$17/each
Servos (3)	\$10/each
Total	\$579

Table 1 – System Cost

5. NETWORK CONFIGURATION

In order to provide central command and control of all robotic systems as well as centrally manage user authentication, we developed a back-end relay server. Running Apache, this server continuously monitors the status of all available systems. By assigning static IP addresses for all remote robots, we were able to routinely maintain an accurate “available” status of whether a robot was online or not. The central server maintained a reservation table of all MAC (media access control) addresses that were registered. Once a robot with a registered MAC address came on-line, it was assigned an address. Commands were sent to and from the robots using UDP (user datagram protocol). The server provides a front-end web site interface where users can connect via HTTP, see a list of all available robots, and view the status of each. In addition, users can view live video feed from any of the robots connected USB cameras without connecting to any specific remote device.

Figure 4 – Server Webpage

Using a central server for this framework provides both scalability as well as security provisions. Scalability is easily achieved by simply increasing the number of available robots. Large scale systems could even include multiple servers organized in either a distributed or hierarchical fashion. The centralized server can also enable secure communications between both the robot and the server and between the user and the server. Even with minimal processing power on the remote hardware platform, performing simple encryption and decryption is achievable. Although not implemented in the current system, encryption schemes are a viable option for preventing intrusions and preventing remote hijacking of the unmanned ground robot. The server based system also provides functionality to strictly control user log in and operation. The server can authenticate users and grant either full functionality or limited access.

6. SOFTWARE INFRASTRUCTURE

6.1. Graphical User Interface

The graphical user interface is a Java web start application which provides control as well as sensor and video feedback. Based on the CMU Robotics Institute TeRK framework [10], the user interface is developed to enable general robotic control as well as platform specific functionality. Launched as a separate application when a user connects to a remote hardware platform, the interface never formally interacts directly with the robot. Instead, it routes all commands and messages through the centralized server which then acts on behalf of the user to forward all requests and to receive all sensory input. This routing provides a means for the system to ensure security throughout its operation. By eliminating the ability for any user to connect directly to a robot, any attempt to breach the robot must be routed through the server. Although not eliminating security threats altogether, this setup significantly reduces the focus of intrusion detection efforts to the server. Any detection of an unauthorized user can easily be handled at the server end.

Figure 5 – Network Launched GUI

The interface itself provides an intuitive graphical means with which to control the robot. Users can control the robot via mouse or keyboard input. The GUI contains a common robotic interface for the functionality common to all robotic platforms: chassis movements, camera pan and tilt movements, video feedback, and connectivity control. At the bottom of the interface, a platform-specific control panel enables users to employ the specific functionality of the remote robot. Such features include sensor feedback, audio control, and battery life. The server displays the robots that are available. When a user clicks on a particular robot, the platform-specific bottom panel adjusts to the robot that was selected.

6.2. Microcontroller Driver

We used existing source code from the Robostix Subversion tree to build a driver for the low-level functions. Using a circular buffer, we processed command bytes based on

certain thresholds for our sensors. If a sensor exceeded this threshold, the microcontroller driver would override the user commands to either alter the path of the robot or to stop and turn the robot to avoid the obstacle. The robot would adjust its path based on which sensor(s) was triggered and what distance was calculated. The sensors integrated with the Robostix microcontroller prevent the operator from running into an obstacle.

6.3. Semi-autonomous Capability

The low-level driver allows for a semi-autonomous mode of operation by adjusting the UGV movement based on sensor information. Since the GUI is client-side, we wanted a quick response in case there were network latencies. Some network delays were as long as 2 to 3 seconds which varied beyond our control. There are many safety concerns if the latency is excessive or if the network link is severed. The Robostix microcontroller provides an immediate response to adjust the robot in these scenarios. Semi-autonomous behavior is also beneficial for the operator who can now “navigate to a target” rather than continually monitoring and dictating every movement.

7. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATIONS

We initially developed and tested our control system on two small, inexpensive platforms – the iRobot® iCreate and the Lynxmotion 4WD chassis. Once we were confident that our design was sound, we ported our system to the Mesa Matilda™. An area of future work, discussed in Section 8, will be to port our system to other military robots.

7.1. Lynxmotion 4WD Chassis and iRobot iCreate

We used the iCreate as our first test platform. This off-the-shelf robot has an open interface and detailed API to allow for rapid testing. We connected our control hardware to the serial port on the iCreate. The Lynxmotion 4WD chassis is a small and rugged platform using common RC tires and 7.2V DC motors for movement. We used a Sabertooth motor controller and built a custom aluminum shelf for our control system. The Robostix generates PWM signals to send to the 2 channels of the motor controller. These two channels allow for mixed mode operation (differential drive). The 4WD chassis has a lithium polymer battery supply powering the motors and electronics.

Figure 6 – iRobot® iCreate and Lynxmotion 4WD Chassis

7.2. Mesa Matilda

The Matilda is a tracked, teleoperated unmanned ground vehicle used in the military and civilian sectors to perform a myriad of missions. These robots are extremely durable, can navigate almost any terrain and are man-portable. Some versions of these small UGVs omit the arm and can be used for search and rescue, reconnaissance, and surveillance. These robots are tough and usually have a variety of cameras and sensors.

Figure 7 – Mesa Matilda with Controller

The Matilda typically operates with its own OCU. By grounding the pendant sense pin, you can by-pass the OCU and send commands directly to the robot over the serial port. The controller has a 31-pin connector with standard RS-232 Rx (receive) and Tx (transmit) pins and operates at 9600 baud, 8 data bits, no parity, and 1 stop bit. A custom cable was made with one end containing the 31-pin connector and the other end to a DB-9 connector. The Matilda protocol consists of command blocks to control its lateral and rotational velocities (throttle and steering), clutch, brake, arm movement, lights, as well as system feedback such as battery life. Both throttle and steering have 7 bits of resolution. These values are sent to a CRC (cyclic redundancy check) function which returns a 16-bit CRC value. An 8-byte block is then sent to the on-board controller. Our hardware implements this protocol in order to control the Matilda and to use our sensor package. The server recognizes the Matilda is available and displays the appropriate GUI when selected.

8. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have presented a realistic design approach for expanding the military's current robotic platforms into truly interoperable systems. We believe that the integration of existing robotic platforms into a common networked system would be in the best interest of not only the military, but also other government and commercial interests. Future

research will focus on implementing our system on UGVs currently in use in Iraq and Afghanistan. We will also research the effect of a smaller, lighter and more powerful processor with better cross-platform integration as well as a more focused effort into the security and information assurance of the entire system.

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